

IMPROVING THE METHODOLOGICAL TRAINING OF FUTURE ELEMENTARY CLASS TEACHERS ON THE BASIS OF INNOVATIVE APPROACHES

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Abstract. *This article describes the content of the work of future primary school teachers in the process of improving their methodological training in mathematics lessons based on innovative approaches, and also emphasizes the degree of effectiveness of the results obtained on the basis of experimental verification.*

Keywords: *pedagogical competence, talent, motivation, innovation, creativity, critical thinking, problem solving.*

Introduction. At the same time, the task of training teachers with new methodological training stood before the higher pedagogical education system. Because the elementary school teacher should acquire the experience of calculating, forming and rooting the psychological and physiological identities of children of 1-4 years of age. It is known that the development of technologies for improving the methodological training of the future elementary school teacher in the educational process takes priority. To do this, students, primary school teachers, are required to be an individual who meets modern requirements, thinks independently, has intellectual potential, deep knowledge, a modern worldview and thorough methodological training.

Literature review. At this point, A.K.Markova recognizes the methodological training of teachers as “a psychic state that allows independent and responsible work, consisting of the results of human labor, the ability and skill of a person to perform certain labor tasks” [3]. Only if it is creatively studied will it be possible to effectively and usefully apply mathematical information. It is a sign that the profession of a teacher requires a creative approach and has tremendous opportunities for the formation of its creativity.

B.S.Abdullaeva describes the following considerations in her scientific work: “the professional potential and level of education of a primary school teacher, child psychology, knowledge of the modern methodology of primary education are important in improving the quality of primary education. It is advisable to form the necessary skills in primary school students, to raise the quality efficiency of primary education to a new level, to introduce modern methods and means of teaching into practice” [1].

American researchers Elizabeth Ann, S.Kelly has conducted an analysis of those that influence student academic achievement internationally in his research. First of all, citing the atmosphere in the house and at school. It has been cited that it affects education if the social condition of students is not good, and that the school environment, in addition to personal homelands, the teacher has classroom technologies, teacher qualifications and high pedagogical skills, and the impact of school resources on education. Among girls and boys, who have cited differences and essence in the level of literacy in mathematics and Natural Sciences in their scientific research [2].

Research Methodology. Today, there is a growing interest in and integration of innovation information technology into the educational process. The application of modern information technology to the educational process is giving students the opportunity to draw conclusions and analyze the knowledge they are learning by searching for and learning independently. In such a pedagogical process, the teacher must comprehensively educate students as a competent person and pay attention to the educational and educational significance of the technologies used.

It requires a methodological-based approach to the content of education in the formation of knowledge, skills and skills intended to prepare future primary school teachers for the profession in higher educational institutions. Methods of teaching mathematics and Natural Science in higher educational institutions literature, dissertations, monographs on the use of pedagogical technologies and international assessment programs in improving the teaching of subjects, improving its effectiveness were analyzed and the necessary conclusions were drawn. In particular, in the course of our study, we interpreted the sources to be discussed as follows, as methodological foundations for improving the methodological training of future primary school teachers:

- ensuring the effectiveness of Education, comprehensive human education, legal and regulatory framework for the training of competitive, competent future teacher personnel (legislation in the field of youth education and training, personnel training, decrees and decisions of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan, legal and regulatory acts of the Cabinet of ministers, relevant ministries, departments and international organizations on the status of teachers);

- international scientific ideas of foreign and mature stylists, educators and psychologists of our country on ensuring the quality of education and training of future teaching staff.

On the basis of these methodological ideas, the qualification requirements for modern teachers are established in a number of international and national legal and regulatory documents.

These considerations will certainly pay off in teaching future primary school teachers to prepare students through international assessment programs with a modern approach to reducing their methodological training. In improving the methodological training of future primary school teachers, it is definitely necessary to pay special attention to interdisciplinary integration.

Analysis and results. Flipped-learning Technology. In this technology, the study of the theoretical part of the subject is carried out outside the audience. In the classroom, however, students complete assignments that require complex cognitive activity while the teacher is in charge. In this situation, the task facing the educator is not to explain the content of the topic, but, on the contrary, to direct the student to the main and difficult aspects of the topic and activate the process of his practical cognitive activity[4]. When this technology is used, students will understand the topic better, the educator's interaction with students will improve, develop critical thinking and make it a component of the learning process[4] and audience time will be spent wisely. In preparation for training, students watch their video lessons at home at a convenient time to see the teacher's comments or questions and explanations in the textbook. In the training session, the teacher gives practical assignments and the necessary additional materials. In the process of completing the assignment, students work alone, in pairs or in groups, while the teacher monitors student activities, identifies the main difficulties in mastering the material, explains complex thoughts and evaluates student work. In teaching in such an approach, the student's role in the auditorium moves to the house, while assignments to the house move to the auditorium, and thus this approach has been called "circular". This approach supports the following pedagogical

processes: in the table below, the traditional and "Flipped-learning" technology is compared(see Table 1:

Table 1

Flipped-learning Technology

Traditional educational technology	Flipped-learning Technology
Start class	Entering the lesson by discussing a new topic
Home task inspection and evaluation	Strengthening a new topic studied outside the audience through assignments
New theme statement	Learning a new topic through presentations by students in pairs and small groups
Strengthening a new topic	Through teacher supervision support as well as evaluation
Giving home a task	Submission of the next new topic

The student learns the theory of a new topic that needs to be prepared outside the audience through a method suitable for him: watching or performing a video or presentation, writing or reading, asking or presenting, and enters the audience with his theoretical knowledge of a new topic, strengthening this knowledge in the auditory. Through this approach, the learning process in an audience can be transformed into a dynamic and controversial learning environment in its own right.

Professional competence of the future elementary school teacher is an activity that reflects the areas of application of the professional capabilities of the teacher. It is possible to form basic competencies in future elementary school teachers. In addition, it is worth noting that these basic competencies create professional competence in them.

The system for improving methodological training is a complex dynamic system, which includes knowledge, skills and qualifications on the basis of the requirements of the state educational standard based on personal and professional characteristics, as well as universal (aesthetic, philosophical, historical), scientific (mathematical, linguistic, methodological), psychological-pedagogical and competency approach to the use of innovative pedagogical and information and communication technologies in practice(see Table 2):

Table 2

Conditions for improving the methodological training of future primary school teachers on the basis of innovative approaches

Conditions for improving the methodological training of future primary school teachers on the basis of innovative approaches	
Organizational process	Psychological-pedagogical process
Conditions for improving the methodological training of future elementary school teachers	Implementation of interdisciplinary integration
Ensuring the testing process of pedagogical activity(material and technical, educational and methodological, e-learning resources, etc.)	Implementation of a methodical preparation-oriented approach in teaching students
Organization of cooperation of educational institutions for improving methodological and mathematical training (OSM-school)	Formation, development and improvement of motives and needs of pedagogical activity

“Boomerang” technology. The peculiarity of this methodology is that it is aimed at educating future teachers in the course of the lesson, working with various literature, texts outside the lesson, keeping the studied material in mind, speaking, being able to freely state the idea, having a lot of information in a short time and being able to evaluate all the student by the teacher during the lesson. One of the important tasks of the training session is the arousal of circumstances that allow to activate the existing knowledge and skills of students on the topic under study, in combination with the individual and group mastery of the materials presented in the implementation of the educational process by future teachers and the control and assessment of the levels of mastering texts and others in

Conclusion Recommendations

In conclusion, the need to improve the methodological training of future primary school teachers is noted by many Methodists, each of whom prefers one direction or another. From this comes the need to conduct a detailed study on the professional training of students for the teaching of mathematics to primary school teachers as the main task of the educational process

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